

A multi-year study on the detection and distribution of domoic acid contamination of shellfish in production areas from Los Lagos Region, Chile (2000-2021)

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Abstract

Domoic acid, a marine neurotoxin causative of Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) was first detected in Chilean shellfish in January 1997. The presence of domoic acid (DA) in shellfish extracts was determined by reverse-phase HPLC-UV. Domoic acid concentrations exceeded in some instances the maximum permitted level (MPL) of 20 mg kg⁻¹ of tissue. The highest levels were found in mussels (*Mytilus chilensis*) and its presence was associated with diatom blooms of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia*. Since the diatoms *P. cf. australis* and *P. cf. pseudodelicatissima* are frequent phytoplankton components with a wide distribution in Chilean coastal waters, a permanent ASP monitoring program was implemented by the National Fisheries Service (Sernapesca) in 2000. Analyses of live shellfish samples collected from production areas from Los Lagos Region (41°30' to 42°30' S) are reported from January 1999 to May 2021. A total of 94 from 57,882 samples (0.16%) were found to contain DA above 20 mg kg⁻¹. Another 1,360 samples (2.35%) contained DA below MPL (0.01 to < 20 mg kg⁻¹). Diatom blooms and domoic acid were detected every year. However, toxicity levels above MPL were observed only in nine of the 22 years of continuous monitoring. Regular increases in toxicity were observed mainly during the transition from spring to summer (October to March) with peaks during December and January. High detoxification rates of DA from mussels ($T_{1/2} < 4 \pm 1$ days) allowed the development of contingency plans during the blooms that minimized harvest closures. Despite its recurrent nature, the risk observed to date has been low, with no reported cases of poisoning in humans, marine mammals, or birds.

Keywords: *Pseudo-nitzschia* diatoms, domoic acid, management, monitoring, mussels

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Introduction

Marine biotoxins of the paralytic and diarrhetic type have caused severe public health and economic impacts in southern Chile (41° - 55° SL) and are produced mainly by toxigenic dinoflagellates, such as *Alexandrium catenella* since 1972, and *Dinophysis acuta* since 1994, respectively (Díaz *et al.*, 2019; Sunesen *et al.*, 2021). In addition, blooms of the potentially toxic pennate diatoms of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* are common and distribute over large coastal areas of Chile (18° to 54° SL) (Suárez-Isla *et al.*, 2002; Alvarez *et al.*, 2009; Pizarro *et al.*, 2017; Díaz *et al.*, 2019).

An early paper by Rivera (1985) reported the presence of several *Pseudo-nitzschia* species in Chile (*P. australis*, *P. calliantha*, *P. cuspidata*, *P. delicatissima*, *P. pungens* and *P. fraudulenta*). The species *Pseudo-nitzschia pseudodelicatissima* and *P. fraudulenta* were described by Espinoza-González *et al.* (2016) and *P. seriata* by Pizarro *et al.* (2017) and Pinto-Torres *et al.* (2018 a, b). Only four toxigenic *Pseudo-nitzschia* species were associated with the production of domoic acid (DA), which was detected in cultures and samples: *P. australis* (Suárez-Isla *et al.*, 2002), *P. calliantha* (Alvarez *et al.*, 2009), *P. seriata* and *P. delicatissima* in the Magallanes region by Pizarro *et al.* (2017), Pinto-Torres *et al.* (2018b) and Díaz *et al.* (2019).

Previous studies have found significant accumulation of DA in mussels, scallops, and a tunicate, well above the regulatory limit of 20 mg kg⁻¹. In November 1999, maximum levels of 330 mg kg⁻¹ were detected in mussels from Chiloé following a bloom with high dominance of *P. australis* (Suarez-Isla *et al.*, 2002). In scallops from Northern

Chile, levels of 103 mg kg⁻¹ were detected during a *P. australis* bloom. (Alvarez *et al.*, 2009). Domoic acid was found in lower concentrations in edible tissues in native sea squirts (*Pyura chilensis* Molina, 1782) (8.7 to 15.5 mg kg⁻¹), showing the complex impact of these blooms on the marine food chain (López-Rivera *et al.*, 2009).

Los Lagos Region (41°30' to 42°30' S) includes the Chiloé archipelago and the Chiloe Inner Sea (Fig. 1). This is a unique ecosystem and an important shellfish aquaculture area (Seguel and Sfeir, 2010). Mussel aquaculture has grown steadily at an annual rate of 12% since 2002. In 2020, more than 495,000 tons were landed, with more than 90% of this production destined for export. This production had a value of more than US\$250 million, and 400,304 tons were accounted for by *Mytilus chilensis* only, while other species were harvested for export and domestic consumption

Annual blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* diatoms and the presence of domoic acid in shellfish have affected the local economy within the Los Lagos Region since 1999 (Figs. 1, 2). We report here the detection and distribution of DA in extracts from Chilean shellfish tissues collected from commercially relevant aquaculture sites and natural beds as part of a national shellfish sanitation program. Domoic acid concentrations exceeded the regulatory level of 20 mg kg⁻¹ of tissue in a few cases. The presence of the toxin was associated with blooms in which pennate diatoms of the genus *Pseudo-nitzschia* were highly dominant (> 90%). These blooms have not been associated to date with confirmed cases

of human Amnesic Shellfish Poisoning (ASP) intoxications, but pose a serious potential public health threat. Because diatoms *P. cf. australis* and *P. cf. pseudodelicatissima* (and others) are common phytoplankton constituents that are widely distributed in Chilean coastal waters, a permanent ASP monitoring program was implemented by the Servicio Nacional de Pesca (Sernapesca) as part of a Chilean National Shellfish Sanitation Program (NSSP, 2021). The NSSP includes over 150 sampling stations throughout Los Lagos Regions (Fig. 1). Weekly samples of live shellfish, phytoplankton, and abiotic parameters were collected by certified samplers. The frequency of sampling was increased during contingencies when causative toxic species and/or toxins were detected. This program also includes analyses of chemical contaminants (pesticides and heavy metals: Hg, Cd and Pb) and microbiological pathogens (*Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*) from lower frequency samples. The data sets are integrated into an on-line early warning system (mr-SAT) for local health authorities responsible for setting precautionary closures.

Materials and Methods

Shellfish samples and analysis

Statutory analyses were performed at the Laboratory of Marine Toxins on live shellfish samples provided by the NSSP. Domoic acid was determined by reverse-phase HPLC analysis with UV detection (after Quilliam *et al.*, 1995; López-Rivera *et al.*, 2005). For each analysis, a sample of 200 g wet weight of shellfish containing between 12 to 18 individuals was used. The method was in-house validated and accredited according to ISO 17025:2017 (LOD = 0.01 mg kg⁻¹).

Certified reference materials were provided by NRCC, (Canada).

Fig. 1. Map of Chile indicating the location of Los Lagos Region. Black circles, sampling stations.

Data sets

Analyses of live shellfish samples collected from production areas from Chiloé archipelago, Los Lagos Region from January 1999 to May 2021 are reported. Shellfish samples (mussels 90%, clams 9%, 1% other) were collected weekly from 102 NSSP sampling sites (Fig. 1). Phytoplankton cell densities were retrieved from data sets from 18 stations from the Institute for Fisheries Research (IFOP) regional monitoring program reports, which include 10 monthly surveys per year (IFOP 2016). Phytoplankton net samples are collected monthly following IFOP methodology (IFOP 2016) and in the areas identified in figure 2. Microscopic identification and concentrations of cells

per liter are obtained from cell counts on Uttermohl chambers. IFOP has been providing time series of phytoplankton distribution and toxin levels along with environmental and oceanographic parameters from the three southernmost regions since 2006.

Results and Discussion

A total of 94 from 57,882 samples (0.16%) were found to contain DA above 20 mg kg⁻¹. Another 1,360 samples (2.35%) contained DA below the MPL (0.01 to < 20 mg kg⁻¹). These results provide the first detailed long-term study of the occurrence and distribution of DA in the Inner Sea of Chiloé (Fig. 2). Diatom blooms and domoic acid were detected every year. However, toxicity levels above MPL were observed in only nine of the 22 years of continuous monitoring.

Fig. 2. Distribution of NSSP sampling stations (in red) and IFOP stations (in blue).

In the Southern hemisphere, the transition from spring to summer occurs in December. To account for the seasonality of the blooms, figure 3 depicts data for the second semester of a given year, followed by the first half of the following year. Toxin detections per sampling station are reported as:

$$\text{Detection rates} = \frac{\text{N}^\circ \text{ of detections} * 100}{\text{total N}^\circ \text{ of analysis per yearly period}}$$

The solid line represents the total number of samples per yearly period. From 2006 to 2021, the average of annual samples was 3,209 ± 302 (9.41% variability).

Regular increases in toxicity were observed mainly during transition periods from spring to summer (October to March), with peaks in December and January.

As shown in figure 4, high DA detoxification rates from mussels ($T_{1/2} < 4 \pm 1$ days) allowed the development of contingency plans during the bloom period that minimized the risk to human health and allowed for short harvest closures.

The seasonal evolution of toxicities of domoic acid in shellfish is indeed related to blooms of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species in the Chiloé Inner Sea. Domoic acid concentrations in shellfish could be related to the densities of *Pseudo-nitzschia* species in some cases.

As reported by others (Bates *et al.*, 2018), the relationship between *Pseudo-nitzschia* species densities and the evolution of shellfish toxicity is a complex issue. The literature is inconclusive regarding toxicity levels of *P. cf. australis* and/or *P. cf. delicatissima* or other species that may be present.

Fig. 3. Detection rates of domoic acid in shellfish samples. Percentage of all assays $>$ LOD from July to June of consecutive years (1999-2021). The red segments correspond to the percentage of samples above the MPL.

Fig. 4. Detoxification of DA in mussels. A single exponential function was fitted to data (mean \pm SD) from seven sampling stations (Sigmaplot 14.5).

The risk of DA intoxications remains low and under control. This is an important result of the NSSP managed by Sernapesca, the regional surveillance programs of the Ministry of Health and the collaborative network of authorized laboratories.

Despite the annual *Pseudo-nitzschia* blooms and seasonal detections of domoic acid, there have been no confirmed cases of poisoning in humans, marine mammals, or

birds. There have been no reported cases of toxic or subtoxic lots being marketed in the last 22 years. The spatial and temporal distribution can be used as a risk map to support management decisions and guide policy decisions by health authorities.

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